

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

PHILOSOPHICAL AND THEOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF BELIEF IN THE AFTERLIFE WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL ORDER AND PROSPERITY

Abuzarova Ulkar

Ph.D., Assistant Professor, Azerbaijan Institute of Theology, Mahammad Nakchivani 29, Baku/Azerbaijan

Abstract

Discussions on the belief in the afterlife have been going on for centuries for its importance concerning the existence of human beings. Both religion and philosophy were areas of these debates. For this reason, it is of great importance to study the subject of the hereafter in the context of its religious and philosophical foundations in terms of its possibility and necessity. As a method, instead of presenting a new solution proposal on the subject and evaluating and defending it in the article, the evidence put forward in both the Islamic and Western theologians' and philosophers' thought systems regarding the possibility and necessity of the hereafter was analyzed and evaluated.

Keywords: religion, belief, afterlife, social order, prosperity

For believers, organising and ordering life according to the faith of God, ensuring the collective peace of humanity, depends on believing in the hereafter, that is, life after death. The belief in the hereafter, which performs its function in this world, is the development of a sense of responsibility and the support of moral values, which is necessary for human beings, whose purpose of creation is to serve God, to create a network of relations based on moral tests and moral rules on earth. In other words, belief in the afterlife aims to positively influence the behaviour of those who prefer it by reminding them of their responsibilities to those who are caught up in temporary interests. Because there is no responsibility in the other world. This is where man will take away his value in the other world. In this sense, the hereafter has an important role in enabling people to reach the highest level desired by religion in this world.

One of the important functions of belief in the afterlife is its impact on society. The actual realization of absolute good morality in worldly life in a continuous, constant and stable manner, without discord and hypocrisy, can only be achieved by believing in the Last Day. Therefore, belief in the afterlife is an indispensable need in social life as a control mechanism that prevents evil and leads to good. In other words, belief in the afterlife makes a positive contribution to human actions. As pointed out before, according to the Qur'ān, the afterlife is the day when the truth is revealed and the moment of decision to be made about the behaviour. On that day, the value of one's behaviour, lifestyle, beliefs and religion will be revealed (Lamont, 1990, p. 198). Therefore, a person who lives his life believing that the hereafter will come true will take care to be more selective in behaviour, thoughts and beliefs. This, on the other hand, is important for the correction of society as an event that starts in individuals and surrounds the society.

Having accurate knowledge of the Qur'ān and hadith, and a genuine understanding of Islam, one knows that the religion gives importance to the life of this world as well as the life of the thereafter. In this sense, belief in the afterlife is a principle of faith that is

not only related to the afterlife but also concerns worldly life. As it is understood from the Qur'ān and hadiths, "the world is the field of the hereafter" and people will deserve their happiness or unhappiness in the hereafter according to their behaviour in this world. From this point of view, "Life is not just preparing for another world. In this respect, "Life is not just preparation for another world. Life also has its own value, and life should be endowed with as much goodness, beauty and wealth as possible by world standards" (Landmann, 1974, p. 104).

Humanist philosopher Corliss Lamont (d. 1995) emphasized that the belief in immortality would be universal in terms of necessity because the idea of the afterlife, which humanity has had in one way or another since humanity has existed, expressed pessimism in some ancient cultures, and on the other hand, he also stated that this belief is unquestionable (Lamont, 1990, p. 198). Lamont did not fail to mention that his belief brings with it requirements that include important reasons (actual truth) to shed light on current realities. In other words, according to him, the search for a universal law that affects every normal person with sound intelligence and education can only be revived thanks to the belief in immortality. (Lamont, 1990, p. 199). In this sense, according to Lamont, some psychological and effective reasons also increase the desire to live forever (Lamont, 1990, p. 199).

If the issue of belief in the hereafter is deeply considered and the evidence on which it is based is thoroughly analyzed, it will be seen that all of them have to do with human morality, deeds, and every aspect of life (Mawdūdī, 1956, p. 205)). It is clear that the belief in the hereafter is effective in the morality of the individual's behaviour and in his orientation towards good values. Because the belief in the hereafter gives people a sense of responsibility and accountability (Mawdūdī, 1956, pp. 28-29). In this respect, Erich Fromm (d. 1980) points out that the fear of death should be treated as a moral problem (Fromm, 1982, p. 177).

The issue of what kind of life will be in the next world is a matter that concerns the individual extremely

much. The conditions of the future life are determined in this worldly life. By placing the conditions of the future life in front of the individual in his current life, it is expected that his/her behaviour will take place within the limits of morality. A person who is not aware that he/she will be held accountable for his deeds cannot be considered to be on the right path. In other words, for a person who lacks belief in the hereafter, the sense of responsibility is weak or even non-existent. It is impossible to satisfy the individual's moral and material needs if the human mind is empty of the subject of "belief in the hereafter". Human beings have a nature and creation that is inclined to sensual pleasures and carnal desires, the crimes of which require punishment. Cruelty, lying, deceit, backbiting, adultery and other similar acts do not have exactly bad consequences in this life. However, since the consequences of these will occur in the hereafter, an individual who believes in the hereafter avoids these deeds. In other words, only the fear of reckoning after death and the fear of punishment can prevent a person from doing so (Fuzūlī, 1962, p. 77).

It is important for the development of the moral value structure that people live with the belief and awareness that the "time" will come at a moment when they will become conscious of all their feelings, thoughts, words, actions and behaviours. The vivid description of how man's inner structure will be revealed on the Day of Judgement in the Qur'ān is a state that Allah desires man to achieve in his life. A person who takes his soul into accounting, being aware of his own shortcomings, puts forward a lifestyle in which he can give an account, and is never afraid that all his thoughts and behaviours will be exposed to people. This, in a way, is a complete translation of the moral personality of the individual from the inside out. Fazlurrahman states that "*taqwa*" (piounes) which is one of the basic terms of Qur'ān, means the union of one's public and personal life (Fazlurrahmān, 1999, p. 215).

Without gaining a sense of responsibility, man cannot comprehend the meaning of life and become aware that he/she is different from other living things in the universe. Therefore this point indicates that the consciousness and sense of responsibility, albeit to a certain extent, is an important reason that reminds people that life does not end with the end some days, in short, about being immortal. The life of this world is neither wholly cruel nor unstable. Many other aspects of human nature, such as responsibility and feelings of regret, are not empty and fruitless if they are content with worldly life, but they are not mentally impossible to complete in another world. Therefore, life after death cannot be considered as a very distant or even impossible future, and the problems that need to be solved in our existence in this life cannot be ignored (Derveze, 1973, pp. 236-237).

Dostoevsky (d. 1881), who drew attention to the turmoil, anarchy and irresponsibility that will arise in a society without belief in God and the hereafter (Dostoyevsky, 1938, II, 242) in his work *The Brothers Karamazov*, said in the same work, "If there is no immorality, there is no virtue" (Dostoyevsky, 1938, I, 66) or "if there is no immortality of the soul, there is no value and everything is permissible" (Dostoyevsky, I, 79).

It is also necessary to focus on another aspect of the belief in the afterlife that is oriented towards the world. For this, it is necessary to deal with the event of death first. As it is known, Socrates was the first to deal with the death subject as a philosophical problem. Socrates states that the fear of death is one of the fears that people have throughout their lives. According to him, the fear of death disappears as soon as the mind perceives death as either becoming nothing or starting a new life (Plato, 1992, p. 60). From this, it becomes clear that the fear of death arises from ignorance about death and beyond. In this sense, death is seen as a stage that human nature must complete, and it is thought that the fear of death and the conviction that death is bad is due to ignorance about life and death (Kindī, 2002, pp. 300-301).

Various studies on the psychology of death have revealed the importance of the effects of belief in the afterlife on the individual and society. The event of death is at the peak of the sense of grief in terms of the damage it causes in the psychology of the individual. In this sense, there is only one fear, and that is the fear of death (Karaca, 2000, p. 148). Only the belief in the hereafter can remove the frightening of the idea that death will bring man to nothingness. If a sane and thinking person believes that his life is purposeless, he will fall into a spiritual depression. In such a case, the only mechanism that saves people from depression is the belief in the hereafter. Only the other hand, belief in the hereafter has an important function in terms of supporting social peace as well as providing psychological comfort for the individual (Koç, 2004, p. 225). In this sense, religion's explanations about death and beyond death, which are perceived as the end of life, are seen as a solution proposal that relieves the individual's tension in the face of death (Koç, 2002, p. 8). On the other hand, since Freud (d. 1939) and the proponents of his views deny the existence of religion itself, he considers beliefs after death as imaginaries invented by individuals for their imagination to overcome their troubles in this world (Freud, 1995, p. 192).

Studies show the positive effects of belief in the afterlife on the behaviour and thoughts of children, young and old people (Feifel, 1959, p. 116). The psychological impact of death on young children, moreover, the death of their relatives in the family, the lack of correct awareness of children on this issue, and the negativity and failures in children's lives accordingly, are a result of research in the field of religious psychology (Karaca, 2000, p. 197; Köylü, 2004, pp. 95-96). On the other hand, it is stated that explaining the death event to children correctly and raising awareness about the subject will contribute to their maturation (Ross, 1997, pp. 15-16). Therefore, belief in the afterlife is important in terms of directing behaviours, and in this respect, it should be kept alive all the time.

The thought that life will end with death at some point disturbs an individual emotionally and cognitively. In this context, the fear of death is closely related to developmental periods. According to psychologist J. B. Pratt, children usually do not doubt whether life will go on. What they have to learn and absorb is the reality of death (Mill, 1969, p. 446). Explaining the event of

death to young children and explaining to them that the most important tool to overcome this fear is to explain to them that death is a part of life, just like eating, drinking, sleeping and other issues. Therefore giving religious education to children explaining that there is life (hereafter) after death, and preparing them for this will make them less shaken by the event of death. This is the first step in raising consciousness and successful people who have a positive outlook on life for the future.

When viewed as one of the belief principles of religion the functionality of the belief in the afterlife can also be evaluated in the context of the functionality of religion. In this sense, it would be appropriate to mention the following statements of Māturīdī here: “People are made to have various desires and different natures. Such dominant egoistic desires are placed in their human structure that if they were left alone with their creation, they would contend with each other in the distribution of benefits, in the seizure of various supremacies, honours, sovereignty and powers. This is followed by mutual hatred and then bloody struggles. In such a case, societies will certainly destroy each other and collapse. However, if the purpose of the universe’s existence were made dependent on it, the wisdom of its existence would be in vain, and its creation would be absurd. Accordingly, they need an “origin” – religion that will reconcile people and prevent them from falling into strife and separation that lead to collapse and extinction (Māturīdī, 2002, p. 5).

Therefore, the functionality of the belief in the afterlife in society emerges in a way that aims to develop a conscious, responsible, successful, fair, charitable, and, finally, moral society. This is one of the ways to believe in the afterlife and at the same time be happy in this world. As partially mentioned before, Farabi (d. 339/950), when talking about political science and the ideal state, sees happiness in the ideal sphere as dependent on happiness in the real sphere and states that societies should achieve a common goal for this (Dieterici, 1890, p. 16). Because human beings were created in such a way that their ultimate happiness is the acquisition of a kind of perfection in another life that exceeds the ordinary conditions of this life. In general, this can occur in a well-organized society based on appropriate laws that organize communities in such a way as to enable everyone to achieve this ultimate goal” (Leaman, 2000, p. 241). In fact, he points out that such a society should be led by someone who will ensure the happiness of the individuals in this world and the hereafter and the health and order of the society in accordance with the conditions of Islam (Fārābī, 1990, p. 16).

Ibn Sīnā’s acquisition of the perfection of the theoretical and practical mind leads one to otherworldly happiness. It should be pointed out that the competence of theoretical and practical reasoning power is related to the concept of justice in Ibn Sīnā’s thought and that they are concepts that express balanced behaviour. That is to say, it is only possible for the soul to stay away from negative characters arising from the wrath of the soul and lustful powers and to gain its happiness after death through justice. According to him, the reason why people are religiously commanded to be righteous

is for the happiness of the soul in the other world. As can be seen, the perfection of the theoretical mind power of the soul is right, and the perfection of the power of the deeds is justice and goodness (Ibn Sīnā, 1924, II, p. 430, 454; Ibn Sīnā, 1987, pp. 119-120; Ibn Sīnā, 1984, p. 100). Ibn Sīnā emphasizes that for the soul to reach virtue and gain happiness, one should not go to extremes and deficiencies in thoughts and behaviours. In this context, for example, Ibn Sīnā considered it necessary for the social order in which people live to acquire the habit of acting in a balanced manner, which is the competence of the moral mind. Therefore according to him, the excess of the practical mental powers, which means going out of balance, is harmful to the person himself, and the excessive state is harmful to the society (Ibn Sīnā, 1924, II, 445; Ibn Sīnā, 1984, pp. 96, 109).

Conclusion

Throughout history, belief in the afterlife has had an important place among the religious beliefs of people in different periods and societies. Belief in the afterlife has been the most important belief after belief in God in many religions. Although it constitutes a category of belief, the afterlife has not only been related to life after death but has also been seen as an issue related to worldly life. For this reason, what is promised in the holy books as reward or punishment in the hereafter, has guided the behaviour and activities of individuals in the life of the world. Like theologians, a significant number of philosophers advocate the view that the morality, deeds and lives of believers have an impact on every aspect of their lives. According to this approach, a person of faith who takes his/her ego into account is aware of his/her shortcomings, reveals a lifestyle in which he/she can give an account, and is never afraid of having all his thoughts and behaviours exposed to people. On the other hand, a person who believes that life is purposeless falls into a spiritual depression. Belief in the afterlife has an important function in terms of supporting social peace as well as providing psychological comfort individually.

References

1. Lamont, Corliss *The Illusion of Immortality*, New York 1990.
2. Ross, Elizabeth Kubler, *On Death and Dying*, New York 1997.
3. Fromm, Erich, *Kendini Savunan İnsan: Ahlak Felsefesinin Psikolojisine İlişkin Bir Araştırma* (trans. Necla Arat), Istanbul 1982.
4. Fārābī, Abu Nasr Muhammed, *al-Madīnatu’l-fādila* (trans. Ahmet Arslan), Ankara 1990.
5. Karaca, Faruk, *Ölüm Psikolojisi*, Istanbul 2000.
6. Fazlurrahmān, *Ana konularıyla Kur’ān* (trans. Alparslan Açıkgenç), Ankara 1999.
7. Dieterici, Friedrich, *al-Farabi’s philosophische abhandlungen*, Leiden 1890.
8. Fuzūlī, Muhammad ibn Sulaiman al-Bagh-dādī, *Matla’u’l-i’tiqād fī ma’rifati’l-mabda’ va’l-ma’ād* (trans. Kemal Işık and Esat Coshan), Ankara 1962.
9. Dostoevsky, Fyodor, *The Brothers Karamazov*, London 1938.

10. Feifel, Herman, "Attitudes Toward Death" *The Meaning of Death* (ed. Herman Feifel), New York 1959.
11. Ibn Sīnā, Abū Alī Husain, *al-Adhaviyye fi'l-maād*, (ed. Hasan Āsī), Beirut 1987.
12. Ibn Sīnā, Abū Alī Husain, *Kitābu'l-Mabda' wa'l-ma'ād* (ed. Abdullah Nurānī and etc.), Tehran 1984.
13. Ibn Sīnā, Abū Alī Husain, *aş-Şifā: al-İlāhiyyāt*, (ed. George Canawati), I-II, Tehran 1924.
14. Kutluer, İlhan, *Erdemli Toplum ve Düşmanları*, Istanbul 1996.
15. Derveze, Muhammad Izzat, *al-Qurān va'l-mulhidūn*, Damascus, 1973.
16. Mill, John Stuart, "Essays on Ethics, Religion and Society" *Collected Works of John Stuart Mill* (ed. J. M. Robson), London 1969, I-XXXIII, 429-492.
17. Kindī, Abū Yūsuf as-Sabbāh, *Felsefī Risāleler* (trans. Mahmut Kaya), Istanbul 2002.
18. Māturīdī, Abū Mansūr Muhammed, *Kitāb at-Tawhīd* (trans. Bekir Topaloğlu), Istanbul 2002.
19. Mawdūdī, Sayyid Abu al-Alā, *İslām Medeniyeti*, (trans. Mehmet Aydın), Ankara 1968.
20. Landmann, Michael, *Philosophical Anthropology* (trans. David J. Parent), Philadelphia 1974.
21. Koç, Mustafa, "Ölüm Korkusu Üzerine Kuramsal Açidan Psikolojik Bir Değerlendirme", *SÜİFD*, VI (Sakarya 2002), pp. 7-20.
22. Koç, Mustafa, "Yaşlılık Döneminde Ölüm Ötesi Psikolojisi Üzerine Bir Alan Araştırması", *CÜİFD*, VIII/1 (Sivas 2004), pp. 203-228.
23. Köylü, Mustafa, "Ölüm Olayının Çocuklar Üzerine Etkisi ve Ölüm Eğitimi", *OMÜİFD*, XVII (Samsun 2004), pp. 95-119.
24. Leaman, Oliver, *Ortaçağ İslām Felsefesine Giriş* (trans. Turan Koç), İstanbul 2000.
25. Plato, Sokrates'in Savunması (trans. Teoman Aktürel), İstanbul 1992.
26. Freud, Sigmund, *Uygurluk, Din ve Toplum* (trans. Selçuk Budak), Ankara 1995.